

Is academic freedom associated with strong science?

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Academic freedom is a well-known and widely discussed concept, recognized as a key element of the academic system. However, while the intrinsic value of academic freedom is widely recognised, there is little empirical evidence that academic freedom has an impact on research productivity and the quality of scientific output. This paper examines the quality of science at the country level. An analysis based on cross-country panel data covering 119 countries over the period 1996-2021 shows that academic freedom at the country level is associated with the future citation impact of papers published by researchers from a country. The higher the level of academic freedom, the higher the citation impact of papers published 3 years later.

1. Introduction

Academic freedom is a well-known and widely discussed concept in the context of higher education and academic research. Academic freedom encompasses the rights of scholars to engage in teaching, research, and scholarly inquiry without undue constraint or censorship (Altbach, 2001; Brickman, 1968). It is recognized as a fundamental human right and value, essential to the flourishing of democratic societies and the progress of civilization. At the heart of academic freedom is the principle of intellectual autonomy, which empowers scholars to pursue lines of inquiry driven by intellectual curiosity and the search for truth. This autonomy is essential not only for the advancement of knowledge, but also for the promotion of critical thinking, innovation, and the development of a strong scholarly community. Academic freedom is a central ideal of the Humboldtian research university, that underpins the integrity and vitality of academic institutions.

When academic freedom is under attack, various actors seek to secure it because it is recognized as a crucial and absolutely required element of the academic system for both teaching and research. In the context of teaching, academic freedom allows educators to explore controversial or challenging issues, present different perspectives and encourage critical thinking among students. By fostering an environment in which ideas can be freely exchanged and debated, academic freedom promotes intellectual growth and the development of informed, engaged citizens. Academic freedom is also essential in the context of research. It protects scholars from external pressures that may compromise the integrity of their work and ensures that scientific inquiry remains grounded in evidence-based reasoning and free from ideological, political, or commercial interference.

However, while the intrinsic value of academic freedom is widely recognised, there is little empirical evidence that academic freedom has a tangible impact on research productivity, innovation and the quality of scientific output. One of the main reasons for this is the lack of systematic and reliable measures of academic freedom in many countries. There are mostly anecdotal case studies of major scientific discoveries (e.g. DNA) or small studies at faculty and university level with conflicting results (see e.g. Karran, 2009). However, the recently released global cross-country Academic Freedom Index (Spannagel & Kinzelbach, 2023) provides an opportunity to conduct such a study. For example, a recent study using this new index shows that academic freedom in a country is positively associated with the number of patent applications and forward citations of patents (Audretsch et al., 2023).

This paper aims to investigate the relationship between academic freedom and the quality of science in different countries. Specifically, the study aims to answer the research question of the relationship between academic freedom in the country and the quality of research as measured by citation impact.

There are several reasons to expect a positive correlation between academic freedom and the quality of science. Academic freedom fosters a culture of open inquiry and critical discourse in which ideas are rigorously tested, challenged, and refined. By encouraging intellectual diversity and debate, it facilitates the cross-fertilisation of ideas and perspectives, thereby fostering innovation and advancing scientific progress. Academic freedom also serves as a safeguard against the distortion of research agendas by political, ideological or commercial interests. In an environment where scholars are free to pursue lines of inquiry based solely on their merit and scientific relevance, rather than on external pressures, the integrity and objectivity of research are maintained. This improves the quality of scientific output, as results are more likely to be robust, reproducible and reflect genuine advances in knowledge. In addition, academic freedom is closely linked to institutional autonomy and the capacity for self-regulation within academic institutions. Institutions that respect academic freedom are better able to establish robust systems of peer review, quality assurance, and ethical oversight that ensure the integrity and reliability of research outputs. This in turn enhances the credibility of scientific endeavour and promotes public trust in the scientific community.

Scientific disciplines may differ in terms of academic freedom, reflecting the epistemological frameworks and societal contexts in which research takes place. STEM disciplines may be more academically free than other disciplines, because they are less bound by politics and ideology (Spannagel et al., 2020). This difference may also affect the relationship between the degree of academic freedom and the quality of research. While natural and physical sciences can develop successfully even in the context of limited academic freedom, social sciences and humanities may suffer more from ideological and political pressures. This means that disciplinary differences should be taken into account when analysing the relationship between academic freedom and quality of science.

2. Data and Method

2.1. Citation impact

Citation impact was based on the in-house version of the Scopus database provided by the German Competence Network for Bibliometrics (snapshot as of 07.2023). Only “Article” and “Review” types were taken into account. Two indicators of citation impact were used: the mean field-normalized citation rate (FNCR, 3-year citation window) and the proportion of papers in the top 10% of most cited papers (PPtop10%, 3-year citation window). For both indicators fractional counting method was used: the number of papers was weighted by the number of countries in a paper. For example, if three countries were mentioned in a paper, each country received 1/3 of the paper. Indicators were calculated for each country for each year from 1996 to 2021. Both indicators are aggregated and there is a risk of an outlier effect. Rogers et al. (2020) found a high variance in the average category normalised citation impact when the sample is less than 200 papers and suggest this number as an analytical minimum for relative citation performance indicators. Following this recommendation, only country-year with 200 or more papers were selected. Countries with at least 10 country-year observations were selected.

2.2. Academic freedom

Academic freedom was measured by the Academic Freedom Index (AFI) (Spannagel & Kinzelbach, 2023). AFI were extracted from the V-Dem Dataset (Version 13, published in March 2023, <https://doi.org/10.23696/vdemds23>) by the V-Dem Institute of the University of Gothenburg. The index is based on five indicators of academic freedom: 1) freedom to research and teach, 2) freedom of academic exchange and dissemination, 3) institutional autonomy of universities, 4) campus integrity, 5) freedom of academic and cultural expression. More than 2,000 experts assess these 5 indicators. The index is obtained by aggregating point estimates drawn from a Bayesian factor analysis model. A high score on the index indicates a high level of academic freedom.

2.3. Confounding variables

Three variables were used as control variables. GDP per capita (in current US\$) and total population are from World Bank data via the WDI R-package: (<https://github.com/vincentarelbundock/WDI>). The share of papers with international collaboration was calculated for each country-year based on the same sample of articles and reviews from the in-house version of the Scopus database used to calculate the citation impact indicators. The paper was classified as internationally co-authored if it affiliated with more than 1 author and more than 1 country. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
AFI	2716	0.69	0.29	0.05	0.98
FNCR	2716	0.55	0.23	0.08	1.37
PPtop10%	2716	0.05	0.03	0.00	0.14
International collaboration (%)	2716	50.69	17.99	12.37	95.89
GDP per capita	2716	14,633.90	18,740.53	110.46	123,678.70
Population	2716	57,749,454.89	172,251,201.70	263,725	1,402,760,000

2.4. Methodology

A linear mixed effects model was used to regress the two country-year citation impact indicators (mean field-normalized citation rate and proportion of papers in the top 10% of most cited papers) on the AFI and confounding variables. The dependent variable is the citation impact indicator per country and year. The independent variable is the 3-year lagged ($t - 3$) academic freedom index per country and year. The control variables are the 3-year lagged GDP per capita, the 3-year lagged logarithm of the total population and the share of papers in international collaboration.

A linear effects mixed model (estimated using REML and nlptwrap optimizer) was fitted by lme4 (Bates et al., 2015). As fixed effects, 3-year lagged AFI, year, 3-year lagged GDP per capita, 3-year lagged logarithm of the total population and share of papers in international collaboration were included to the model. Citation impact indicators vary between countries and each country has its own mean, so each country should have its own intercept in the model. Slopes can also vary between countries, so each country should have its own slope in the model.

As random effects, country intercepts and country random slopes for the effect of AFI and all control variables were included in the model.

3. Results

3.1. Mean field-normalized citation rate

Table 2 shows the results of mixed effects regression models with and without control variables. The effect of 3-year lagged AFI on FNCR is statistically significant and positive even with included control variables (beta = 0.12, 95% CI [0.06, 0.19], $t(2688) = 3.60$, $p < .001$). The higher the AFI, the higher the FNCR of the papers published 3 years later.

3.2. Proportion of the 10% most frequently cited papers

The effect of 3-year lagged AFI on PPtop10% is statistically significant and positive even with included control variables (beta = 0.0098, 95% CI [0.001, 0.02], $t(2688) = 2.26$, $p = 0.024$). The higher the AFI, the higher the PPtop10% of the papers published 3 years later.

Table 2. Main analysis of the effect of academic freedom index on citation impact

	FNCR	FNCR	PPtop10%	PPtop10%
(Intercept)	0.3601 *** (0.0227)	0.0750 (0.1617)	0.0226 *** (0.0029)	-0.0033 (0.0190)
AFI (t-3)	0.1995 *** (0.0409)	0.1240 *** (0.0345)	0.0222 *** (0.0055)	0.0098 * (0.0043)
Year	-0.0002 (0.0008)	0.0007 (0.0011)	0.0002 * (0.0001)	0.0002 (0.0001)
GDP per capita [log] (t-3)		0.0060 (0.0073)		0.0011 (0.0009)
Population [log] (t-3)		0.0179 * (0.0078)		0.0012 (0.0010)
International collaboration (%)		-0.0009 * (0.0004)		0.0000 (0.0000)
N countries	119	119	119	119
Observations	2716	2716	2716	2716

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$ *** $p < .001$

3.3. Robustness check

To check the robustness of these results, the same linear effects mixed models were fitted with three different lags for AFI, GDP per capita, and population (2 years, 4 years, and 5 years). The effect of the AFI on citation impact is robust across different lags. For FNCR 2-years lagged beta = 0.1283 ($p < .001$), 4-years lagged beta = 0.1177 ($p = .003$), 5-years lagged beta = 0.1294 ($p < .001$). For PPtop10% 2-years lagged beta = 0.0123 ($p = .004$), 4-years lagged beta = 0.0108 ($p = .015$), 5-years lagged beta = 0.0123 ($p = .005$).

3.4. Analysis of different fields

Two citation impact indicators were also calculated for four research field supergroups (Social Sciences and Humanities, Life Sciences, Physical Sciences, Health Sciences) identified on the basis of the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) Codes used in the Scopus database. Tables 3 and 4 show the results of mixed effects regression models for different research field. The effect of AFI on FNCR is statistically significant and positive for Life Sciences (beta = 0.1262, $p < .001$), Physical Sciences (beta = 0.2158, $p < .001$) and Health Sciences (beta = 0.0958, $p = .013$). Only for Social Sciences and Humanities the relationship between AFI and FNCR is not statistically significant (beta = -0.0934, $p = .092$). The results for second indicators of citation impact are different. The effect of AFI on PPTop10% is statistically significant and positive only for Physical Sciences (beta = 0.0150, $p = .014$). For Life Sciences and Health Sciences effect of AFI is not statistically significant (beta = 0.0052, $p = .202$ and beta = 0.0072, $p = .061$, respectively). For Social Sciences and Humanities effect of AFI on PPTop10% is negative (beta = -0.0149, $p = .008$).

Table 3. The effect of academic freedom on FNCR in different fields

	Social Sciences and Humanities	Life Sciences	Physical Sciences	Health Sciences
(Intercept)	1.1196 *** (0.3094)	0.0325 (0.2272)	0.3030 (0.2127)	-0.2404 (0.1723)
AFI (t-3)	-0.0934 (0.0553)	0.1262 *** (0.0373)	0.2158 *** (0.0511)	0.0958 * (0.0385)
Year	0.0088 *** (0.0016)	0.0019 (0.0014)	0.0031 (0.0017)	-0.0020 (0.0017)
GDP per capita [log] (t-3)	0.0001 (0.0144)	0.0353 *** (0.0090)	0.0019 (0.0105)	0.0432 *** (0.0072)
Population [log] (t-3)	-0.0316 * (0.0135)	0.0074 (0.0099)	0.0111 (0.0120)	0.0189 * (0.0085)
International collaboration (%)	-0.0010 (0.0011)	-0.0017 *** (0.0004)	-0.0037 *** (0.0009)	0.0000 (0.0006)
N countries	65	85	90	87
Observations	1348	1903	2068	1925

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$ *** $p < .001$

Table 4. The effect of academic freedom on PPTop10% in different fields

	Social Sciences and Humanities	Life Sciences	Physical Sciences	Health Sciences
(Intercept)	0.1314 *** (0.0388)	-0.0628 ** (0.0195)	-0.0228 (0.0237)	-0.0125 (0.0167)
AFI (t-3)	-0.0149 ** (0.0057)	0.0052 (0.0041)	0.0150 * (0.0061)	0.0072 (0.0038)
Year	0.0010 *** (0.0002)	0.0002 (0.0002)	0.0002 (0.0002)	-0.0001 (0.0002)
GDP per capita [log] (t-3)	-0.0007 (0.0020)	0.0062 *** (0.0012)	0.0030 * (0.0014)	0.0039 *** (0.0008)
Population [log] (t-3)	-0.0049 ** (0.0017)	0.0016 * (0.0008)	0.0020 (0.0013)	0.0008 (0.0008)
International collaboration (%)	0.0003 * (0.0001)	0.0002 *** (0.0000)	-0.0002 (0.0001)	0.0001 (0.0001)
N countries	65	85	90	87
Observations	1348	1903	2068	1925

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$ *** $p < .001$

4. Conclusion

Is academic freedom associated with strong science? An analysis based on global cross-country panel data covering 119 countries over the period 1996-2021 shows that academic freedom at the country level is associated with the future citation impact of papers published by researchers from a country. The higher the level of academic freedom, the higher the citation impact of papers published 3 years later. These results are robust across different lags (2, 4, 5 years). This finding means that, in general, academic freedom seems to be associated with strong science.

However, when science is split down into different fields, the results are mixed. The most robust positive relationship between academic freedom and citation impact is observed for Physical Sciences. For Life Sciences and Health Sciences, the effect of AFI is observed for only one out of two indicators. Social Sciences and Humanities show the most controversial results: no effect for one indicator of citation impact and a negative effect of academic freedom for another indicator. This result can be explained both by the nature of the relationship between academic freedom and quality of science and by the specificity of the bibliometric data used. First, the two citation indicators used in the study may not be as good for the social sciences and humanities as for other fields. Second, the coverage of the social sciences and humanities in Scopus is worse than for other fields. Only 65 countries met to the criteria used in the study and were included in the analysis. Further analysis is needed to understand the details of relationships between academic freedom and quality of science.

Open science practices

The data used in this study were extracted from three sources. AFI were extracted from the open source V-Dem Dataset (Version 13, published in March 2023,

<https://doi.org/10.23696/vdemds23>). GDP per capita and total population are from the World Bank data extracted from the open source WDI R-package: <https://github.com/vincentarelbundock/WDI>. Citation impact indicators are based on the in-house version of the Scopus database provided by the German Competence Network for Bibliometrics. As Scopus is a proprietary database, the raw data cannot be made openly available.

Competing interests

Author has no competing interests.

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